

APRIL 27-28, 2023

SOLUTIONS AND ASPECTS OF THE SECURITY SYSTEM APPLICATIONS FOR
SMART CITIES

Temirova Dilfuza Khusanovna¹, Gayratov Zafarjon Kamoliddinovich²

¹Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi, assistant of department “Networks and Systems of Transferring Data”.

²The Samarkand branch of TUTT named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi, assistant of department “Telecommunication engineering”,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7860871>

Abstract. *Smart cities are evolving globally and many governments have invested large sums of monies to develop smart cities. This development is not a result of an overnight decision but rather, smart cities have evolved through a period of time, directly from earlier work on the digital city to ubiquitous city, green city, connected city, sustainable city, eco-city etc. The present age sees the arrival of very high-speed wireless 5G connectivity, fast GPU multi-core-based servers, big data, cloud computing, artificial intelligence, and data analytics. Many of these new technologies have supported the development and realisation of smart cities. In this study, the authors present an outline of security for smart cities and provide a deeper understanding of what we meant by securing smart cities. They discuss the applicability of existing security methods of authentication, access control, encryption, firewalls, and their appropriateness to defending a smart city. Specifically, we cover the security of data, internet, water supply, electricity supply, city brain, and other critical city services and present the possible malicious attacks on a smart city and consequences. Finally, they discuss security best practices for smart cities.*

Keywords: *smart city, smart economy, security, security, environmental security, information and communication technologies, internet of things, city, world experience, rating, socio-economic development, spatial organization*

INTRODUCTION

Environmental, demographic, economic or spatial issues require smarter solutions in the face of the networked community. With population growth and rapid urbanization, we need smart approaches that help create economically, socially and environmentally sustainable cities.

In fact, we can call a city Smart if services and infrastructure are provided using information and communication technologies.

ICTs enable more efficient, flexible, sustainable smart city operations [4]. Intelligent services will transform the city and its inhabitants technologically, governmentally, economically and socially.

The term "Smart City" did not have a clear definition until recently. The concept emerged from the Smart Growth movement (Smart Growth) of the late 1990s, which supports the new urban planning policy [5].

Smart approach Growth , urban development decisions affect our health, education, taxes, transportation, environment, economic growth, equity, opportunities, housing prices, neighborhood security. In other words, they affect everything from our personal lives to our communities and nations. To overcome the side effects of urban development, smart growth

strategies can help maintain and develop attractive, comfortable, security and healthy urban environments.

A smart city is a relatively new concept for the improvement of social and economic urban space. The purpose of the introduction of technology is to improve the living conditions of the urbanized population, to solve environmental and demographic problems. Various innovative solutions, most often related to the IT sphere, help in the implementation of such programs: digital tags, video surveillance systems, centralized public transport, etc.

World megacities are making more and more efforts every year to create a truly smart living environment. Large Russian cities do not lag behind them. Among them, of course, Moscow. You will learn about what technologies represent the concept of a smart city, how it all works and where it is best implemented, from our material.

THE MAIN COMPONENTS OF THE SECURITY SMART CITY

The project involves the construction of a hierarchical complex information system of the "house-district (city)" level. The project identifies the following five main components of the integrated system " Security intellectual city :

1. Technogenic security. Purpose - to ensure the protection of citizens and urban facilities, including GIOP, from the impact of hazardous processes caused by damage and destruction of structural, thermal, water, energy systems, errors in operation and unauthorized impacts.

The component includes the following subsystems at the "house" and "district" levels:

- control and management of water supply, sanitation,
- control and management of gas supply,
- monitoring of mechanical deformations of housing and communal services, GIOP, social facilities,
- fire warning
- control of elevator equipment.

2. Environmental security. Purpose - monitoring the ecological state of the air and the water basin to ensure the protection of citizens and the natural environment from the possible negative impact of economic activity. The component includes the following subsystems at the "district" level:

- control displacement transport funds recycling household waste,
- control of the movement of snowplow vehicles.

3. Transport security. The purpose is to ensure the protection of citizens in transport, transport infrastructure facilities and vehicles from illegal interference.

The component includes the following subsystems at the "district" level:

- radio frequency identification of vehicles,
- information support of stops , parking / parking lots .

4. Public security. The purpose is to ensure the personal protection of citizens in places of residence, in adjacent territories, in places of mass recreation, at cultural, architectural and historical sites.

The component includes the following subsystems at the "house" and "district" levels:

- video surveillance brownies and adjoining territories ,
- intercom and identification,

APRIL 27-28, 2023

- panic button (“citizen-policeman”) on social facilities,
- control and management of access to social facilities.

5. Energy efficiency and resource saving. Purpose - to ensure the optimization of costs and consumption of energy resources, water resources, thermal resources by social, housing and communal and other facilities.

The component includes the following subsystems at the "house" and "district" levels:

- control And control brownie And street lighting ,
- control of consumption and supply of electricity.

Depending on the purpose of the subsystems and components, the main consumers of the results of the functioning of the integrated security system are the dispatch centers of the district administration and the city center for monitoring and decision support. At the top hierarchical level (from a technical point of view), the complex system simulates the development of the current situation, thereby performing not only the functions of monitoring, but also managing various elements of the city's infrastructure. The transmission of information from subsystems to control rooms is carried out by radio electronic means via radio and wire channels.

Picture 1. The main components of the complex system "Security Smart City"

Advantages of the Smart City system:

- reduction in overall energy consumption - up to 30%;
- increase in water use efficiency by 20%;
- reduction in the level of crime - up to 30%;
- reduction of traffic jams and travel time - up to 20%.

Security City. The introduction of a centralized city security system can significantly reduce the level of crime and the risk of terrorist attacks, improve the coordination of law enforcement and emergency services, and prevent or reduce the consequences of major

accidents. An integrated urban security system is built on the basis of a single urban situational center, whose functions include:

- environmental pollution monitoring;
- monitoring significant infrastructural, administrative, cultural objects (SMIS And SMIK)
- receiving signals from panic buttons;
- receiving emergency calls with automatic location of the subscriber;
- processing data on the detection of dangerous goods in transport;
- video surveillance camera data processing, video analytics ;
- Public notification.

On the video surveillance system as part of an integrated urban security system. Such a system should have the following features:

- face and license plate recognition;
- automatic detection of wanted persons and vehicles;
- notifications about recorded crowds.

Transport. Benefits of smart city traffic management:

- reduction of traffic jams;
- cost reduction for city services;
- improving the efficiency of emergency services;
- growth of investment attractiveness of the city.

Intelligent management of urban traffic flows is carried out from a single dispatch center, in which the following data is processed:

- location of emergency transport;
- location of special equipment;
- information about the movement of urban transport;
- data on accidents and congestion.
- city station network charging electric vehicles ;

Telemetry of urban engineering networks. The solutions developed by INTELVISION allow monitoring urban gas systems, water supply and sanitation systems, as well as electrical networks. The solution for urban engineering networks includes:

- remote monitoring of systems in real time;
- generation of reports and analytical summaries, data visualization;
- automatic notifications about accidents;
- predictive modeling.

Housing and communal services. Digitalization of housing and communal services plays an important role in the development of the Smart City

Solution Digital Housing and communal services include:

- remote collection of readings from subscriber metering devices for utilities;
- remote collection of readings from metering stations of resource-supplying organizations;
- automatic notifications about accidents, leaks, non-payments;
- remote control.

APRIL 27-28, 2023

World experience in the implementation of smart cities. There are only a few completed smart city projects in the world, however, several hundred cities around the world are at the stage of applications, design, construction and implementation of adopted programs. According to South Korean researcher Jung- Hoon Lee (Jung-Hoon Lee) from Yonsei University (Yonsei University) in the world as of 2012, there were 143 projects of "smart (green) cities" of varying degrees of completion. Including 35 projects in North America, 11 in South America, 47 in Europe, 40 in Asia, 10 in the Middle East and Africa . cities and Communities "smart city theme covers more than 800 cities. China unveiled its Smart city , where more than 200 cities are planned to be developed. According to another source²⁵, there are only two examples of “smart cities” in the world so far – Tianjin Eco City in China and Kashiva-ho-ha Smart City in Japan.

The United Nations predicts that 70% of the world’s population will be living in cities and urban areas by 2050, meaning emissions and energy usage will continue to rise with every passing year. The need for smarter urban transport networks, environmentally-friendly water disposal facilities, and buildings with high energy efficiency are more critical than ever.

This is where smart city programs and initiatives come in. Incorporating smart technology including the Internet of Things (IOT) – objects that are embedded with sensors for data exchange – in urban cities not only improves the quality of life of its citizens but also the overall public safety.

Picture 2. Smart City Monitoring Dashboard

IoT platform for the Internet of Things and M2M. INTELVISION has developed its own Russian IoT platform for Smart City/Internet of Things and Industrial Automation (IIoT) solutions.

Smart unity IoT - integration a platform for deploying modern combined (wired and wireless solutions based on LoraWAN technology) solutions for automation, dispatching, telemetry, business intelligence, remote monitoring and maintenance of IoT and M2M systems, providing digital transformation of industrial enterprises, IT companies and cities. The platform and vertical solutions created on its basis also help system integrators, equipment manufacturers,

operators and service providers to develop and implement their own Internet of Things and Smart City solutions, running both on local servers and in the cloud.

CONCLUSION

In this paper we analyzed the main components of the security smart city. Smart city security infrastructure can take several forms, from university campuses to industrial complexes to legitimate and thriving metropolises. But while the possible configurations may be broad, the use cases are narrower than they initially seem. The emergence of the original gated communities is just a magnification of an unfortunate reality throughout the world: that peace of mind often requires a sizeable investment. But since smart surveillance systems are inherently affordable and scalable, they can create better community equity by providing efficient security to everyone.

REFERENCES

1. Bhushan B., Khamparia A., Sagayam K.M., Sharma S.K., Ahad M.A., Debnath N.C. Blockchain for smart cities: A review of architectures, integration trends and future research directions. *Sustainable Cities Soc.*, 61 (2020), Article 102360
2. Manguri K.H., Omer S.M. SDN for IoT environment: A survey and research challenges. *ITM Web of Conferences*, vol. 42, EDP Sciences (2022), p. 01005
3. Rathore S., Kwon B.W., Park J.H. BlockSecIoTNet: Blockchain-based decentralized security architecture for IoT network. *J. Netw. Comput. Appl.*, 143 (2019), pp. 167-177
4. Esposito C., Ficco M., Gupta B.B. Blockchain-based authentication and authorization for smart city applications. *Inf. Process. Manage.*, 58 (2) (2021), Article 102468